

Core Optimization Study on a SMR with Neutronics/Thermal-hydraulics Coupling and Investigation on Thermal Power Uprate

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ABSTRACT

Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) that offer greater flexibility and lower construction investment compared to large-scale pressurized water reactors have become an attractive option for developing countries. Due to the limited experience with SMRs, further research is still required to enhance SMR's safety and economic performance. The core inlet flow distribution can be adjusted by modifying the hydraulic resistance characteristics at fuel assembly inlets. Without changing the core physical dimension, the real-time optimal match between local power and coolant flow throughout the fuel life-cycle can effectively flatten the outlet temperature distribution and suppress the local hot spot temperature, which is of great significance for improving operational safety. Moreover, the optimized system allows for higher thermal power under the same safety margins, which can enhance the reactor economic competitiveness. To this end, a 200 MW natural circulation SMR was selected as the reference case. Coupled neutronics/thermal-hydraulics calculations were performed using the CFACT and COBRA IIC/MIT-2 codes, while the global optimal inlet resistance distribution was determined using the genetic algorithm. The results indicate that under nominal operating conditions, the optimized design significantly reduces the maximum outlet temperature throughout the fuel cycle. Even with a 10% power uprate, the optimized core maintains a minimum outlet subcooling greater than 5 °C, satisfying all relevant safety limits.

Keywords: SMR, core optimization, neutronics/thermal-hydraulics coupling, power upgrade

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, Small Modular Reactors (SMRs) have attracted increasing attention worldwide [1]. Compared to general pressurized water reactors, SMRs offer greater flexibility in site selection and possess strong potential for integration with various renewable energy sources, making them particularly suitable for the increasingly diversified energy demands and the global trend toward low-carbon development [2].

Although significant progress has been made in the development of various SMR technologies in recent years, there remains room for improvement to make SMR core designs more attractive. Without altering the core physical dimension, enhancing the reactor operational parameters within acceptable safety margins, can effectively improve its economic competitiveness [3]. From the perspective of core thermal-hydraulic design, adjusting the hydraulic resistance at the assembly inlets (e.g. installing various throttle orifices) to redistribute the coolant flow among assemblies contributes to a better match between the local power and coolant flow within the core, thereby reducing hotspot temperatures and achieving a more uniform coolant temperature field [4]. Under the same safety margins, the system with optimized flow distribution allows for a certain increase in reactor power, thereby expanding its potential application scenarios and enhancing overall economic viability.

At present, several studies have been conducted on core flow distribution optimization, yet certain limitations remain: (1) the time-dependent variation of power distribution throughout the fuel cycle

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has not been adequately considered; and (2) the neutronics feedback effects induced by changes in flow distribution are overlooked, i.e., the thermal-hydraulic and neutronic fields are treated in a fully decoupled manner [4], [5], [6], [7].

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Minimize } f(K_{in,1}, K_{in,2}, \dots, K_{in,n}) &= \max\{\Delta T_1, \Delta T_2, \dots, \Delta T_m\} \\ \text{Subject to } L_i \leq K_{in,i} \leq U_i, i &= 1, 2, \dots, n \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where $K_{in,i}$ is the inlet resistance coefficient of the i -th fuel assembly, L, U stand for the lower and upper bound of the resistance coefficient, respectively; $\Delta T_k = T_{max,k} - T_{ave,k}$ is the difference between the highest and average core outlet temperature at the k -th time node for the fuel life-cycle.

In this study, a 200 MW water-cooled SMR is selected as the reference case. The optimization objective is to minimize the outlet temperature of the hottest channel over the entire fuel life-cycle, with the inlet hydraulic resistance coefficients of fuel assemblies serving as design variables. To address the multi-extremum global optimization problem expressed in Eq. (1), a representative metaheuristic method—the Genetic Algorithm (GA)—is employed, which has been widely utilized and validated in fuel loading pattern optimization in the nuclear engineering. To enable a more comprehensive analysis of the flow distribution optimization process, the Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics (N/TH) coupled solution approach based on operator-splitting technique is adopted. Finally, in the context of thermal power uprate, the safety parameters of the optimized and non-optimized systems are compared to evaluate the practical potential of the proposed optimization scheme.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1. Optimal Inlet Resistance Scheme Search using Genetic Algorithm

2.1.1. Fitness function

To solve the core flow distribution optimization problem, the adaptive Genetic Algorithm (GA) is adopted in this study, which is a metaheuristic algorithm inspired by the mechanisms of inheritance and evolution in natural biological systems [8]. In GA, the initial population evolves through selection, crossover, and mutation over successive generations until a stopping criterion is met, converging to global optimal solutions based on the defined fitness function. For the current flow distribution optimization problem, the fitness function is defined as:

$$\begin{aligned} FF_i &= \exp(\alpha \cdot f_i) \\ \text{where } f_i &= \begin{cases} C - \Delta T_i, & \Delta T_i \leq C \\ 0, & \text{others} \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where α is the scaling transformation coefficient for the fitness function, C represents a conservative estimate of the objective function limit; through evaluating and ranking the population fitness, superior candidates can be identified and subsequently used to generate the next population.

2.1.2. Operators

In the present work, the binary coding strategy is utilized to transform the real-value input variable (inlet resistance coefficient) into a 0/1 string for genetic manipulation. The population evolves in successive generations using following genetic operators: (1) **Selection**: Use stochastic universal sampling plus elitism to form the next generation from the current population; (2) **Crossover**: After the selection operation, the adjacent parent individuals are paired and the adaptive crossover probability P_c defined in Eq. (3) is compared with a random number. If the random number is lower than P_c , the segments after the random position on parents' chromosomes are exchanged and two offspring are generated; (3) **Mutation**: A random number is drawn and compared with the adaptive mutation probability P_m in Eq. (4). If the mutation is triggered, a random position on the chromosome (0/1 string) is chosen and the corresponding bit is flipped.

$$P_c = \begin{cases} P_{c1} - \frac{(P_{c1} - P_{c2})(FF - FF_{ave})}{(FF_{max} - FF_{ave})}, & FF \geq FF_{ave} \\ P_{c1}, & FF \leq FF_{ave} \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

$$P_m = \begin{cases} P_{m1} - \frac{(P_{m1} - P_{m2})(FF - FF_{ave})}{(FF_{max} - FF_{ave})}, & FF \geq FF_{ave} \\ P_{m1}, & FF \leq FF_{ave} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Where $P_{c1} = 0.9$, $P_{c2} = 0.6$, $P_{c1} = 0.1$, $P_{c1} = 0.001$; FF is the fitness value of an individual population; FF_{ave} and FF_{max} denote the average and the maximum fitness value of the population, respectively.

2.2. N/TH Coupling Scheme

The reactor N/TH coupling calculations can be categorized into two types: (1) tight coupling and (2) loose coupling methods [9]. In the tight coupling method, the neutron transport equations and the thermal-hydraulic conservation equations are solved simultaneously, yielding higher computational accuracy but posing greater development complexity. In contrast, the loose coupling method solves these equations separately and achieves coupling by exchanging boundary condition information between the equation sets. The latter can fully utilize existing codes and has been widely studied.

Figure 1. Diagram of data exchange between neutronic and subchannel codes.

Among the loose coupling solution approaches, operator-splitting is a mature and widely used method for N/TH coupling [10]. This technique allows two validated codes to be coupled in a straightforward manner. In this study, the subchannel code COBRA calculates the core inlet flow distribution as well as the local fluid and solid temperatures. Based on the given thermal-hydraulic parameters, the deterministic-method-based code CPACT solves the neutron transport equations to obtain the neutron flux and power distribution in the core. These two codes are coupled via file exchange and a driver program, as illustrated in Figure 1. In summary, the flow distribution optimization process, based on GA-driven optimal inlet resistance search and coupled N/TH calculations, is shown in Figure 2.

2.3. Codes

CPACT is a nuclear design code for LWRs developed at Tsinghua University. After years of development and upgrades, it has achieved high computational accuracy. The calculation results by CPACT have been benchmarked against those from CASMO-SIMULATE, SICENCE, and MCNP, demonstrating its reliability [11]. For LWR neutronics calculations, CPACT can rapidly compute key parameters such as k_{eff} , power distribution, control rod worth, and temperature coefficients.

Developed by MIT (Massachusetts Institute of Technology), COBRA IIIC/MIT-2 is an extended version of the COBRA-IIIC subchannel code [12]. Compared with the original code, this version incorporates temporal and spatial acceleration terms into the momentum equations to improve the quality of conservation equations. Additionally, refined closure models and modified water properties are implemented in the code. COBRA IIIC/MIT-2 can compute the flow and enthalpy distribution in rod bundle or the full reactor core under both steady-state and transient conditions.

Figure 2 Flow chart of GA-driven flow distribution optimization with N/TH coupling.

3. CASE STUDY

3.1. Description of selected SMR

In this study, a 200 MW integral low-temperature reactor with full-power natural circulation is selected as the reference case. Designed by the Institute of Nuclear and new Energy Technology, Tsinghua University, this reactor also falls within the category of small modular reactors (SMRs) [13].

Figure 3. Core configuration of 200 MW natural circulation SMR.

The 200 MW natural circulation SMR adopts an integral primary loop layout with an internal hydraulic control rod driven system. Compared with conventional PWR nuclear power plants, it offers enhanced safety and greater flexibility in site selection, and is suitable for diverse applications, including steam supply, district heating, and desalination. Figure 3 depicts the core configuration of the 200 MW SMR. The overall parameters of the reactor core in the current design are summarized in Table I.

Table I. Main parameters of 200 MW natural circulation reactor.

Parameter	Unit	Value
Core thermal power	MW	200
Core pressure	MPa	8
Inlet/outlet coolant temperature	°C	232/280
Inlet coolant mass flow rate	kg/s	855
Active region length	cm	210
Active region equivalent diameter	cm	222
Average enrichment of refueling assemblies	--	~3%
Number of fuel assemblies	--	208
Core configuration	--	208 cartridge fuel assemblies; 52 cruciform control rods
Fuel assembly configuration	--	9×9 rod array (77 fuel rods, 4 water rods)
Equilibrium fuel life-cycle	year	>2
Average burnup depth of discharged assemblies	MW·d/tU	>30000
Reactivity control and reactor shutdown system	--	Hydraulic control rod driven system
Emergency reactor shutdown system	--	Boron injection system

3.2. Core Modeling in Neutronic and Thermal-Hydraulic Codes

In the CPACT code, the neutron transport module performs assembly homogenization and generates a cross-section library. Subsequently, the cross-section processing module generates cross-section data for all nodes under the specified core conditions. The core diffusion equation is then solved using the Green's function nodal method. After obtaining the nodal power distribution, the intra-assembly reconstruction module calculates fuel rod power distribution. The output files are automatically integrated into the COBRA input deck, providing detailed three-dimensional core power data. Due to the core symmetry, both CPACT and COBRA models simulate one-quarter of the core. Figure 4 demonstrate the detailed geometry modeling of core.

Figure 4. Core modeling in CPACT and COBRA (not to scale).

In this study, the radial and axial peak power factor, maximum fuel centerline temperature, MDNBR, peak cladding temperature and minimum outlet subcooling before and after optimization are compared to evaluate the optimization effects, where the MDNBR (Minimum Departure from Nucleate Boiling Ratio) is the thermal-hydraulic safety metric. Considering the parameter range of the 200 MW reactor, the AD-Barnett correlation[14] is employed to calculate the local DNBR within assemblies at all burnup points, thereby determining the in-core MDNBR.

3.3. Optimization under Nominal Conditions

Figure 5 presents the distribution of inlet resistance coefficients for the obtained optimal scheme. Overall, higher resistance coefficients are assigned to the peripheral assemblies, while lower values are applied to the inner ones. This trend arises because the peripheral assemblies maintain relatively lower power levels and are sufficiently cooled throughout the reactor's lifetime, whereas the central high-power assemblies require increased coolant flow for adequate heat removal. For the current optimization problem and the selected parameter settings of the AGA algorithm, the convergence to the optimal solution is achieved after 115 generations, as shown in Figure 6.

Figure 5. Distribution of inlet resistance coefficient for the optimal scheme.

Figure 6. Evolution of objective function value during optimization process.

(a) Objective function

(b) Core parameters

Figure 7. Comparison of objective function and core parameters during fuel life-cycle

A comparison of the objective function values during fuel life-cycle before and after optimization is given in Figure 7(a). The 650-day equilibrium life-cycle is uniformly divided by a 50-day interval, forming 14 burnup nodes. The optimized objective function value, $T_{max} - T_{ave}$, shows a remarkable reduction, particularly during the later stage of the life-cycle. Figure 7(b) compares the neutronic and thermal-hydraulic parameters before and after optimization. In terms of thermal-hydraulics, the optimized core exhibits significantly improved safety characteristics, as the minimum outlet subcooling margin increases notably (indicating effective suppression of the hot-channel temperature), and the MDNBR also uprates. On the other hand, the neutronic parameters show negligible variation, suggesting that the current flow distribution optimization scheme does not substantially affect the core's neutronic characteristics. The pin-by-pin power comparison at day 0 (Figure 8) further confirms this conclusion.

Figure 8. Pin-by-pin power at Day 0; (a) without optimization, (b) without optimization.

3.4. Investigation on the Effect of Power Upgrade

The results in Section 3.2 demonstrate that the optimized scheme effectively enhances operational safety margins under the same operation conditions. To further explore the potential of the core and assess its safety performance, a power uprate analysis is conducted. For the selected natural circulation SMR, an increase in core power leads to higher core flow rate, outlet pressure, and inlet temperature. Consequently, the outlet subcooling margin and local DNBR are also affected. When the core thermal power is increased by 10%, the minimum outlet subcooling margin throughout the life-cycle before and after optimization is shown in Figure 9. It can be observed that although the flow rate rises correspondingly with power, the increased heat generation and the reduced inlet subcooling result in a significant decrease in outlet subcooling. For the unoptimized case, the minimum subcooling margin drops below the safety criterion of 5 °C, whereas the optimized configuration still satisfies the safety requirement and the MDNBR value is 3.82, which remains well above the design limit (1.35).

Figure 9. Comparison of outlet subcooling with and without optimization after thermal power uprate

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper proposes a flow-distribution-optimization-based approach to improving core parameters for a SMR. To overcome the limitations of traditional flow distribution optimization studies that decouple neutronic and thermal-hydraulic calculations, an operator-splitting technique is employed to couple the core physics code CPACT with the subchannel code COBRA IIIC/MIT-2. The adaptive genetic algorithm is adopted to address the complex optimization problem involving multiple burnup nodes and fuel assemblies. The optimization objective is to minimize the maximum-to-average core outlet temperature difference $T_{max} - T_{ave}$ during the life-cycle via inlet resistance rearrangement. A 200

MW natural-circulation SMR is selected as the reference case. The results show that, compared with the unoptimized case, the $T_{max} - T_{ave}$ throughout the fuel life-cycle is decreased by 38.1%, and the MDNBR is also improved slightly, indicating enhanced operational safety. Moreover, the influence of flow distribution optimization on neutronic parameters is minor. When the core thermal power was increased by 10%, the unoptimized core no longer satisfies the design limit for minimum outlet subcooling, whereas the optimized core continues to meet safety requirements, and the corresponding MDNBR remains within acceptable limits. These results demonstrate that the proposed optimization scheme effectively enhances core performance and further exploits the potential of the reactor.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Asuega, B. J. Limb, and J. C. Quinn, “Techno-economic analysis of advanced small modular nuclear reactors,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 334, p. 120669, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.120669.
- [2] J. I. Lee, “Review of Small Modular Reactors: Challenges in Safety and Economy to Success,” *Korean J. Chem. Eng.*, vol. 41, no. 10, pp. 2761–2780, Oct. 2024, doi: 10.1007/s11814-024-00207-0.
- [3] S. Bahaiddin Alam, D. Kumar, B. Almutairi, P. K. Bhowmik, C. Goodwin, and G. T. Parks, “Small modular reactor core design for civil marine propulsion using micro-heterogeneous duplex fuel. Part I: Assembly-level analysis,” *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, vol. 346, pp. 157–175, May 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.nucengdes.2019.03.005.
- [4] Z. Chen, P. Zhao, G. Zhou, and H. Chen, “Study of core flow distribution for small modular natural circulation lead or lead-alloy cooled fast reactors,” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 72, pp. 76–83, Oct. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2014.04.032.
- [5] H. Xu, Y. Wang, and H. Xie, “A preliminary analysis on optimization of core flow distribution,” *Prog. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 146, p. 104147, Apr. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.pnucene.2022.104147.
- [6] E. Zhu *et al.*, “Research on multi-objective optimization method for flow distribution of natural circulation reactor during its life-cycle,” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 176, p. 109266, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109266.
- [7] J. Y. Cai *et al.*, “Program development for mass flowrate distribution optimization in the nuclear power plant,” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 184, p. 109681, May 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2022.109681.
- [8] J. H. Holland, “Genetic Algorithms and the Optimal Allocation of Trials,” *SIAM J. Comput.*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 88–105, Jun. 1973, doi: 10.1137/0202009.
- [9] J. Wang, Q. Wang, and M. Ding, “Review on neutronic/thermal-hydraulic coupling simulation methods for nuclear reactor analysis,” *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, vol. 137, p. 107165, Mar. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.anucene.2019.107165.
- [10] M. Vazquez, H. Tsige-Tamirat, L. Ammirabile, and F. Martin-Fuertes, “Coupled neutronics thermal-hydraulics analysis using monte carlo and sub-channel codes,” *Nucl. Eng. Des.*, vol. 250, pp. 403–411, Sep. 2012, doi: 10.1016/j.nucengdes.2012.06.007.
- [11] Z. Liu and Y. Hu, “CPACTC a quick and precise physics analysis code for in-core fuel management,” in *Proceedings of the GLOBAL 2009 congress - The Nuclear Fuel Cycle: Sustainable Options and Industrial Perspectives*, 2009, pp. 287–287. URL <https://inis.iaea.org/records/dwr37-57k79>
- [12] J. W. Jackson and N. E. Todreas, “COBRA IIIc/MIT-2: a digital computer program for steady state and transient thermal-hydraulic analysis of rod bundle nuclear fuel elements. Final report,” Massachusetts Inst. of Tech., Cambridge (USA). Energy Lab., PB-82-180233; MIT-EL-81-018, Jun. 1981. URL <https://www.osti.gov/biblio/5059627>
- [13] Hao W., Zhang Y., Yang X., and Guo W., “Characteristics and heating market applications of NHR200-II, a small, modular integrated full-power natural circulation reactor,” *J. Tsinghua Univ. Sci. Technol.*, vol. 61, no. 4, pp. 322–328, 2021, doi: 10.16511/j.cnki.qhdxxb.2021.25.025.
- [14] P. G. Barnett, “A comparison of the accuracy of some correlations for burnout in annuli and rod bundles,” Jan. 1968. Accessed: Feb. 10, 2026. URL <https://www.osti.gov/etdweb/biblio/20885142>